

Conductivity, thermal and morphological properties of nano MgO dispersed PVC-PEG polymer composite electrolytes

D. Ravindran^{*a} and P. Vickraman^b

^aDepartment of Physics, Thiagarajar College of Engineering, Madurai-625 015, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : ravi4xyz@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Physics, Gandhigram Rural University, Dindigul-624 302, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : Nano-sized MgO particles were synthesized through sol-gel method and dispersed as filler in PVC-PEG matrix with lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) as dopant salt. The content of MgO particles in the electrolyte was varied to study its influence on the ionic conductivity of the membranes. The electrolyte films were subjected to XRD, AC impedance analysis. The analysis reveals the strong influence of MgO particles on the conductivity profile. The conductivity of MgO doped electrolyte membranes exhibits two maxima one occurring at 1 wt% and other at 6 wt% of filler. The film with composition (PVC-PEG-PC-LiClO₄-MgO) : (19-15-50-10-6) exhibits higher conductivity of 6.034×10^{-6} S/cm at room temperature. Ten times enhancement in the conductivity value was observed. The thermal stability of the membrane was estimated through TGA analysis. The SEM analysis shows the porosity and connectivity of the pores was determined by the MgO content.

Keywords : Polymer electrolyte, ionic conductivity, SEM analysis, thermal analysis.

Introduction

Solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) has emerged as promising electrolyte materials for applications in all solid-state lithium batteries, super capacitors, electrochromic devices, etc.¹. Polymers have the important attribute of flexibility that facilitated the design of solid-state rechargeable batteries. SPE has many advantages over their counterpart liquid electrolyte such as processing flexibility, but their conductivity at room temperature is usually too low for device application. Polymer gel electrolytes (GPE) are characterized by higher ambient ionic conductivity values compared with solid polymer electrolyte. They are generally prepared by adding large amount of liquid plasticizer to the SPE matrix. They consist of a polymer network swollen in a solvent and acquire both cohesive properties of solids and diffusive transport properties of liquids. The capability of gel electrolyte to act as both the separator and the electrolyte leads to easy fabrication and allows the possibility of miniaturized devices. Owing to this dual characteristics gel or plasticized polymer electrolytes find a variety of applications. The addition of plasticizer leads to number of drawbacks. The one of the major setback preventing the successful working of lithium

polymer batteries is the reactivity at the Li/Li⁺ interface and development of a passivation layer at the Li-metal surface causing an increase in the internal resistance. These electrolytes lose their mechanical strength due to the addition of plasticizers². Composite polymer electrolytes (CPE) are synthesized by dispersing a small fraction of micro/nano-size inorganic/ceramic filler particles in to the conventional SPE³. The CPE shows significant improvement in the mechanical strength of the films as well as interfacial activity at the electrode/electrolyte interface by restricting the formation of the passivation layer which causes an increase in the internal resistance of the battery. In CPE, the particle dimension and filler content play an important role because the addition of small amount of filler may collapse the chain-organization of the polymers which in turn facilitates higher ionic conduction. Recently, Ulaganathan *et al.* reported that addition of nano BaTiO₃ in (PVdF-HFP)/PVAc increases the amorphous region in the blend matrix hence enhances the conductivity⁴.

The nano scale metal oxides have attracted a great deal of research interest due to their wide range of applications. Among them, magnesium oxide (MgO) has at-

tracted considerable interest because of its peculiar properties. MgO is highly insulating crystalline solid with NaCl crystal structure with outstanding properties such as chemical inertness, electrical insulation, high temperature stability, high thermal conductivity and secondary electron emission⁵. In the present work, we have synthesized the nano MgO filler and incorporated in PVC-PEG blend matrix as filler with LiClO₄ as salt to investigate its influence on the conductivity, thermal and morphological properties of the electrolyte membranes.

Experimental

Magnesium oxide nanoparticles were synthesized using the following procedure. 200 g of MgCl₂ powders was dissolved in the distilled water. To this concentrated solution of NaOH was added dropwise under constant vigorous stirring. The milky suspension of Mg(OH)₂ particles were produced. The suspension was boiled for 30 min. Then fine powders are filtered. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with de-ionised water to remove the chloride ions. Mg(OH)₂ precipitate was calcinated at 400 °C for 4 h to produce MgO particles⁶. Poly vinyl chloride (PVC) of average molecular weight 60,000 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used after drying under vacuum at 60 °C for 24 h. Poly ethylene glycol (PEG) (mol. wt. = 200) was procured from CDH, India. Propylene carbonate was purchased from Merck and LiClO₄ from Sigma-Aldrich, dried by annealing under vacuum at 120 °C for 24 h. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was procured from Merck and used as solvent. The appropriate amounts of PVC, PEG and LiClO₄ were dissolved in THF under constant stirring. After complete dissolution, MgO particles are added and the resulting solution was stirred continuously for a period of 10–12 h. The resulting highly viscous slurry was cast and the residual solvent was allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. The films were further dried in a temperature-controlled oven at 50 °C for 24 h and preserved in desiccator.

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

The crystalline nature of the composite electrolyte film was examined using JEOL, JDX 8030 X-ray diffractometer at room temperature. XRD patterns of pure PVC, PEG, and LiClO₄ are shown in Fig. 1(a-c). The broad peak

corresponding to PVC shows the amorphous nature of the polymer. The two prominent peaks of PEG (at $2\theta = 19.2^\circ$ and at $2\theta = 23.4^\circ$) show the crystalline nature of polymer. The diffraction pattern of synthesized MgO particles after calcinated at 400 °C for a period of 4 h is indicated in Fig. 1(d). The diffraction pattern coincides well with earlier reported result⁷. The average crystallite size of samples was determined by Debye-Scherrer's formula : $k\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$, where k is a constant, λ the X-ray wavelength (0.15409 nm), β full wavelength at half maximum and θ is half diffraction angle. The average particle size determined using the above formula is 24 nm. Fig. 1(e,f) shows the diffraction patterns of film without filler and 6 wt% of filler. The peaks pertaining to the salt are found disappearing in the composite electrolyte film. This indicates the absence of excess of salt in the complexed polymer films. The appearance of broader peak in the composite film indicates the reduction in the crystallinity of the membrane which is desirable for ion mobility.

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of (a) PVC, (b) PEG, (c) LiClO₄, (d) MgO, film with (PVC : MgO), (e) (25 : 0), (f) (19 : 6).

Conductivity analysis :

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy is employed to study the conduction mechanism observing the participation of the polymeric chain, mobility and carrier generation processes. The conductivity was determined using the relation $\sigma = l/R_b (\pi r^2)$, where l is the thickness of the electrolyte film, r the radius of the membrane and R_b is the bulk resistance obtained from the plots of real impedance (Z_r) against imaginary impedance (Z_i). The film with composition (PVC-PEG-PC-LiClO₄-MgO) = (19-15-50-10-6) exhibits higher conductivity of 6.034×10^{-6} S/cm at room temperature. The conductivity of a polymer electrolyte can be described by the relation, $\sigma =$

$\Sigma \mu_i n_i q_i$, where μ represent the mobility, n concentration and q the charge of the conducting species. The variation ionic conductivity at room temperature with respect to the content of dispersed nano MgO filler is shown in Fig. 2. The conductivity features two maxima one occurring at 1 wt% and the other at 6 wt% of filler. The first conductivity maximum is possibly due to the dissociation ion aggregates/undissociated salt into free ions with the addition of filler particles. The decrease in conductivity after the first maxima is related with the formation of ion pairs and bigger-sized ion clusters due to reassociation of free ions. The second conductivity maximum is attributed to the formation of a conducting interfacial space-charge layer at the filler/polymer interface, which promotes ion transport⁸. The decrease in conductivity after the second maximum is related to the blocking effect of filler particles, which hinders the motion of mobile ions⁹. But beyond this optimum level, the addition of filler increases the viscosity of the system which hindered the ion mobility.

Fig. 2. Variation of conductivity with concentration.

SEM analysis :

The surface morphology of the samples was examined by JEOL, JSM-840A scanning electron microscope. Fig. 3 shows the SEM images of film (a) without filler, and (b) with 6 wt% filler. The SEM images of both the films exhibits interconnected network of pores. The presence of pores shows the occurrence of phase separation in the electrolytes, which are necessary for the transportation Li⁺ ions between the electrodes¹⁰. The addition of filler results in the disruption the network structure and increases the pore size. Similar behavior was found in TiO₂ doped PVdF-PVC polymer electrolytes in which the porous region was widened with addition of 2.5 wt%

Fig. 3. SEM images of film (a) without filler (b) with 6 wt% filler.

of filler¹¹. Due to the immiscibility of PVC with the plasticizer, the electrolyte films have a phase separated morphology consisting of the plasticizer-rich phase and PVC-rich phase. The plasticizer rich phase provides a pathway for ionic conduction. The PVC-rich phase act as a mechanical stiffener. The plasticizer-rich phase appeared as the pores in the SEM image. Among the two images of films without filler and with filler, the latter exhibits larger pores hence it contains higher plasticizer-rich phase and lower PVC-rich phase that leads to higher conductivity as the plasticizer-rich phase inter-connected through a labyrinth of channels for ionic transport.

TGA analysis :

Thermal analysis has been widely employed to examine all physical processes involving the weight changes. The thermogravimetric analysis curve of the sample with 6 wt% of filler is shown Fig. 4. The degradation curve shows three distinct regions where the film degrades gradually up to 110 °C with 15% weight loss. This could be due to the evaporation of moisture absorbed by the sample during loading or the evaporation of residual solvent. The sample suffers a gradual weight loss from 110 to 260 °C. Further the sample suffers nearly 40% weight loss from 260 to 290 °C. The TGA curve is consistent with the earlier reported result in PVC-PEG-TiO₂ system¹². From the curve it is evident that the film stable up to 110 °C.

Fig. 4. TGA curve of the film with 6 wt% filler.

Conclusion

Polymer composite electrolyte with PVC-PEG blend as matrix, LiClO₄ as salt and propylene carbonate (PC) as plasticizer was synthesized. Nano sized magnesium oxide (MgO) particles were prepared and incorporated as filler. The XRD analysis shows the disappearance peaks related to lithium salt indicating the salt is completely solvated by the system. The impedance analysis reveals the strong influence of filler particles on the conductivity profile of the membranes. The morphological study shows the enlargement of plasticizer-rich phase due to the addition of filler. The thermal stability of the membrane was ascertained through TGA analysis.

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